

"E PUR SI MUOVE": INTERPRETATION AND INCOMPLETENESS IN INDIRECT TRANSLATION

Clare Vassallo

Professor, University of Malta

Email: clare.vassallo@um.edu.mt

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"It's a well-known fact that a translation is no substitute for the original. It's also perfectly obvious that this is wrong. Translations are substitutes for original texts. You use them in the place of a work written in a language you cannot read with ease."

(Bellos, 2011: 34)

Ideas and knowledge travel through time, space, cultures and language through translation. That much is clear to us all. Simply by watching the news we know what's happening all over the world in languages we do not know and, as audiences, we take this for granted.

But what happens if we look closely at texts, say literary texts, and compare sources to targets? How much is changed in translation? Can we depend on translation to give us the same in a different language, at a different time? And how are these differences compounded when we have translations of translations?

Critical analysis of literary texts in translation presents particular problems for the literary critic, but not necessarily for the reader of that text. And exercises in back translation will reveal spaces and differences between all three texts. There is no perfect translation, and the differences will only grow in indirect translation.

We consider translation an act of interpretation, just as readings are interpretations - and both are incomplete. A text, especially a literary text, can contain many acceptable readings which implies that each reading is itself incomplete. In translation the "interpretation which precedes [it] establishes which and how many of the possible consequences and connotations suggested by the original words may be eliminated" (Eco:) and, depending on strategies of domestication or foreignization, how many additional meanings might be added. Translation becomes an act of negotiation which provides readers with an incomplete, interpretative rewriting of a source text - which, in indirect translation is itself another incomplete rewriting of a source.

Indirect translation is part of the "afterlife" of texts alluded to by Walter Benjamin. Texts are changed and adapted to different cultures, times and audiences - and it is through change that they live on. Indirect translation is that next part of a textual journey when the incomplete, re-interpreted and re-written text finds new soil, the seed is planted, and new ideas may grow. But, as P.B. Shelly observed, the new plant is of the same species, but not identical to the one that gave the seed.